

**FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES AT DIFFERENT
LEVELS OF EDUCATION**

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Abstract:

Innovations introduced into the continuous education system create the need for methodical, pedagogic-psychologically analytical study of the problem of formation of cognitive competences in students along with knowledge, skills, qualifications.

Key words: communication, CLT (Communicative Language Teaching), teaching approaches, simulation method, language learning activities

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Introduction

This need requires identifying the didactic factors of introducing a modern approach to the teaching process, improving the methodical system by integrating multimedia educational tools, pedagogical technology and electronic learning environment. Pedagogical-psychological foundations of developing electronic tools based on a modern approach in improving the educational process, requirements and structural structure of information resources, content of multimedia electronic educational resources, methods of use, formation of cognitive competencies of students through the use of media educational resources methodology is important. Based on modern approaches, didactic requirements for the development of textbooks and educational manuals, e-learning resources corresponding to the content of education were studied.

Methods

At the moment, many people are trying to improve their English language by studying different approaches to the English language. This process involves learning English in a variety of ways, including travel, study abroad, media, and the Internet. The overwhelming demand for English has created a great need for quality language education. Hence, the way teachers teach and organize the content which is beneficial to simulate is the most significant of all. Today, modern teachers who teach language students have developed a method of teaching with techniques that develop speech through scaffolding problems. This article deals with one of the methods of teaching English - the communicative approach of the language. This article focuses on the study of the effectiveness of using teaching methods in English classes. Because it can improve students' understanding of the language. In addition, learning to communicate allows students to become more confident in communicating with other people, and they enjoy speaking more. There is detailed information about the relevance of learning English, the role of the teacher. In language learning, the main

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components of learning communication and related language learning activities are mainly based on communication.

Results

Communicative language teaching (CLT), or the communicative approach, is an approach to language teaching that emphasizes interaction as both the means and end goal of learning. Language learners learn and practice the target language in an environment that uses CLT techniques by interacting with each other and with the teacher, studying and using "authentic texts" (in a natural state of language learning). Students working as autonomous language learners both in class and outside of class is effective in developing communication. This method also encourages students to integrate their own experiences into the language learning environment and focuses on experience in addition to learning the relevant language. Today, language learning has taken on a new meaning; learning a foreign language seemed difficult before because there was lack of language practice surrounding. Today, in the period of learning foreign languages, teachers consider communication to be the most effective and it is carried out through various exercises, and in this way the language is used in practice. Communication develops all language skills - from speaking and writing to reading and listening. The goal is to teach the student to speak a foreign language not only effectively, but also correctly. The rules and meanings of new words are taught by the teacher to the student using familiar words, basics and grammatical information, gestures and facial expressions, drawings and other aids. They can also use computers and multimedia, Internet, TV programs, newspapers, magazines, etc. All this helps to arouse students' interest in the history, culture and traditions of the country where the language is being studied. In foreign language lessons, the teacher creates situations in which the students are in pairs and with each other, in groups, through mutual question and answer. This makes the lessons more interesting and colorful. Students demonstrate independent speech while working in groups. They can help each other in correcting the information of the interviewees. The teacher in the class is responsible for the tasks of organizing the dialogue, the facilitator asking questions, conveying ideas to the initial ideas of the participants and acting as a confidant in the discussion of controversial issues. Unlike other methods based on vocal language and repetition and memorization, the communicative approach "Simulation" method organizes outputs: the process is organized through case studies while students are immersed in their actions. This increases students' interest in the lessons: everyone participates with meaningful topics. They often use speaking (reading and writing as well as listening) tasks in classes. At the same time, teachers speak less and listen more, only directing the students' activities. The teacher introduces the exercise, then "talks" to the students, then disappears into the background and acts as an observer and judge. He prefers to use research language only.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the communicative approach is a comparison of learning with the communication process, more precisely, based on the fact that learning is a model of the communication process, although it is somewhat simplified, but even in the main parts it is the same as the real communication system. is different. All of the above about the interactive approach to learning to speak a foreign language allows us to emphasize that the subject of education in this case is speaking a foreign language. In this way, the division of speech skills is clearly visible, and exercises are prescribed for their continuous formation.

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